

GAPS IN DENSE SIDON SETS

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Abstract

We prove that if $A \subset [1, N]$ is a Sidon set with $N^{1/2} - L$ elements, then any interval $I \subset [1, N]$ of length cN contains $c|A| + E_I$ elements of A , with $|E_I| \leq 52N^{1/4}(1 + c^{1/2}N^{1/8})(1 + L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8})$, $L_+ = \max\{0, L\}$. In particular, if $|A| = N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$, and $g(A)$ is the maximum gap in A , we deduce that $g(A) \ll N^{3/4}$. Also we prove that, under this condition, the exponent $3/4$ is sharp.

1. Introduction

We say that A is a Sidon set if all the sums $a + a'$, $a \leq a'$, are different. Erdős and Turan [5] proved that if $A \subset [1, N]$ is a Sidon set then $|A| \leq N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$. On the other hand, Bose and Chowla [1] proved that if $N = p^2 + p + 1$, then there exists a Sidon set $A \subset [1, N]$ with p elements; i.e, the upper bound (1.1) is sharp except for the error term.

Sidon sets of large size have notable properties of regularity. In [7], M. Koluntzakis proved that the elements of a Sidon set of large size, $|A| \sim N^{1/2}$, are well distributed in the classes of residues of small modulo. See [5] for an elementary proof of this result.

Erdős and Freud [4] proved that if $|A| \sim N^{1/2}$ then the elements of A are well distributed in the interval $[1, N]$.

Theorem A (Erdős-Freud). *Let $c > 0$ and $A \subset [1, N]$ a Sidon set with $|A| \sim N^{1/2}$ elements. Then, any interval of length cN contains $\sim cN^{1/2}$ elements.*

S.W. Graham [6] has proved a more precise result.

Theorem B (S. Graham). *Let $A \subset [1, N]$ be a Sidon set with $N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$ elements. Then, any interval of length cN contains $cN^{1/2} + O(N^{3/8})$ elements.*

If we denote by $g(A) = \max_{a_{k-1}, a_k \in A} \{a_k - a_{k-1}\}$ the maximum gap in A , from the Theorem B it is easy to deduce that if A is a Sidon set $A \subset [1, N]$ with $N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$, then $g(A) \ll N^{7/8}$.

In this paper we shall use an identity (Lemma 2.1), which was introduced in [2] and [3], to obtain a better result.

Theorem 1.1. *Let $A \subset [1, N]$ a Sidon set with $N^{1/2} - L$ elements. Then, any interval of length cN contains $c|A| + E_I$ elements of A , with*

$$|E_I| \leq 52N^{1/4}(1 + c^{1/2}N^{1/8})(1 + L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8}), \quad L_+ = \max\{0, L\}.$$

In particular we deduce from this theorem the following corollary for gaps.

Corollary 1.1. *If $A \subset [1, N]$ is a Sidon set and $|A| = N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$, then $g(A) \ll N^{3/4}$.*

It is easy to see that the exponent $3/4$ is the best possible if $A \subset [1, N]$ is a Sidon set with $|A| = N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$. Consider $N = p^2 + p + 1$, and a Sidon set A , $A \subset [1, N]$ with $p \geq \sqrt{N} - 1$ elements. If we split the interval $[1, N]$ in intervals of length $\lceil N^{3/4} \rceil$, then, one of them contains less than $2N^{1/4}$ elements. If we remove these elements from A we have a Sidon set A' with $|A'| = N^{1/2} + O(N^{1/4})$ elements and $g(A') \gg N^{3/4}$.

We don't know how to derive a better estimate for $g(A)$ when the error term is less than $N^{1/4}$. It is related with the difficulty of improving the error term in the upper bound for finite Sidon sets. It would be interesting to know a good upper bound for $g(A)$ when A is a Sidon set of maximal size. Maybe, it is possible an upper bound like $g(A) \ll N^{1/2+\epsilon}$.

It should be noted that the classical construction of Erdős and Turán [5] of Sidon sets, $A_p = \{2kp + (k^2)_p : k = 0, 1, \dots, p-1\}$, gives $g(A) \ll N^{1/2}$ for these sets. It seems not to be the case for the Ruzsa's construction [8] of finite Sidon sets. Numerical and heuristic arguments suggest that $g(A)/N^{1/2} \rightarrow \infty$ in this case. In particular, it would imply that the Erdős's Conjecture, $F(N) \leq N^{1/2} + O(1)$, is not true.

2. Proofs

The proof of the following lemma can be found in [2] or [3].

Lemma 2.1. *Let $A \subset [1, N]$ be a sequence of integers. Then, for any integer $H \geq 1$ we have*

$$2 \sum_{1 \leq h \leq H} d(h)(H-h) = \frac{H^2|A|^2}{N+H-1} - H|A| + D_H,$$

where

$$D_H = \sum_{1 \leq n \leq N+H-1} \left(A(n) - A(n-H) - \frac{H|A|}{N+H-1} \right)^2,$$

$A(n)$ is the counting function of A and $d(h) = \#\{h = a - a'; \quad a, a' \in A\}$. \square

$A(n) - A(n - H)$ is the number of elements of A lying in the interval $(n - H, n]$ and the quantity $\frac{H|A|}{N+H-1}$ is the expected value of $A(n) - A(n - H)$. Then, D_H is a measure of the distribution of the elements of A in the interval $[1, N + H - 1]$.

The argument of the proof of the Theorem 1.1 is the following: If $|A|$ is close to $N^{1/2}$, (L small), then D_H is “small” and consequently, the number of elements of A lying in intervals of length H is “close”, at least in average, to the expected number. From that we can deduce a “good” distribution in any interval $I = (\alpha N, \beta N]$. Upper and lower bounds for the error $E_I = |A \cap I| - (\beta - \alpha)|A|$ are obtained in two different steps (Lemma 2.3 and Lemma 2.4).

Lemma 2.2. *If $A \subset [1, N]$ is a Sidon set with $|A| = N^{1/2} - L$ then, for any integer H we have*

$$D_H \leq \frac{3H^2L_+}{N^{1/2}} + \frac{H^3}{N} + 2HN^{1/2}$$

where $L_+ = \max\{0, L\}$.

Proof. We apply Lemma 2.1 to the sequence A . Since A is a Sidon set, hence $d(h) \leq 1$ for any integer $h \geq 1$ and $2 \sum_{1 \leq h \leq H-1} d(h)(H-h) \leq H^2$. Also we use the trivial estimate for the size of a Sidon set, $|A| \leq 2N^{1/2}$.

$$\begin{aligned} D_H &\leq H^2 - \frac{H^2|A|^2}{N+H-1} + H|A| = \frac{H^2N + H^3 - H^2 - H^2|A|^2}{N+H-1} + H|A| \\ &\leq \frac{H^2(N-|A|^2)}{N} + \frac{H^3}{N} + 2HN^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

If $L \leq 0$, then $D_H \leq \frac{H^3}{N} + 2HN^{1/2}$.

If $L > 0$, then $D_H \leq \frac{H^2}{N}(N^{1/2} + |A|)L_+ + \frac{H^3}{N} + 2HN^{1/2} \leq \frac{3H^2L_+}{N^{1/2}} + \frac{H^3}{N} + 2HN^{1/2}$. \square

Let $I = (\alpha N, \beta N]$, $c = \beta - \alpha$ and we write $|A \cap I| = c|A| + E_I$. We will choose $H = \lfloor N^{3/4} \rfloor$ in all the proofs.

Lemma 2.3. $E_I \leq 10N^{1/4}(c^{1/2}N^{1/8} + 1)(L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8} + 1)$.

Proof. We write $I_H = (\alpha N, \beta N + H]$, then $cN + H - 1 \leq |I_H| \leq cN + H + 1$. We have

$$\sum_{n \in I_H} A(n) - A(n - H) \geq H|A \cap I|,$$

since each $a \in A \cap I$ is counted H times in the sum. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in I_H} \left(A(n) - A(n - H) - \frac{H|A|}{N + H - 1} \right) &\geq H|A \cap I| - \frac{|I_H|H|A|}{N + H - 1} \\ &= E_I H + H|A| \left(c - \frac{|I_H|}{N + H - 1} \right) \geq E_I H - H|A| \frac{(1 - c)(H + 1)}{N + H - 1} \geq E_I H - \frac{H^2|A|}{N}. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$E_I \leq H^{-1} \sum_{n \in I_H} \left(A(n) - A(n - H) - \frac{H|A|}{N + H - 1} \right) + \frac{H|A|}{N}.$$

Now we apply Cauchy's inequality, Lemma 2.1 and the trivial estimates $|A| \leq 2N^{1/2}$, $N^{3/4}/2 \leq H \leq N^{3/4}$ to get

$$\begin{aligned} E_I &\leq H^{-1}|I_H|^{1/2}D_H^{1/2} + \frac{H|A|}{N} \\ &\leq H^{-1} \left((cN)^{1/2} + (H + 1)^{1/2} \right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}HL_+^{1/2}}{N^{1/4}} + \frac{H^{3/2}}{N^{1/2}} + \sqrt{2}H^{1/2}N^{1/4} \right) + \frac{H|A|}{N} \\ &\leq 2N^{-3/4} \left(c^{1/2}N^{1/2} + \sqrt{2}N^{3/8} \right) \left(\sqrt{3}N^{1/2}L_+^{1/2} + N^{5/8} + \sqrt{2}N^{5/8} \right) + 2N^{1/4} \\ &\leq 10N^{1/4} \left(c^{1/2}N^{1/8} + 1 \right) \left(L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8} + 1 \right). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.4. $-E_I \leq 52N^{1/4}(c^{1/2}N^{1/8} + 1)(L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8} + 1)$.

Proof.

$$\sum_{n \in I_H} A(n) - A(n - H) \leq H \left(|A \cap I| + |A \cap (\alpha N - H, \alpha N]| + |A \cap (\beta N, \beta N + H]| \right).$$

We apply Lemma 2.3 to the intervals $(\alpha N - H, \alpha N]$ and $(\beta N, \beta N + H]$ to obtain an upper bound for the last two terms.

$$\begin{aligned} |A \cap (\alpha N - H, \alpha N]| + |A \cap (\beta N, \beta N + H]| &\leq 2\frac{H}{N}|A| + 20N^{1/4} \left(\frac{H^{1/2}N^{1/8}}{N^{1/2}} + 1 \right) \left(L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8} + 1 \right) \\ &\leq 4N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/4}(L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8} + 1) \leq 44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n \in I_H} \left(A(n) - A(n - H) - \frac{H|A|}{N + H - 1} \right) &\leq H|A \cap I| - \frac{|I_H|H|A|}{N + H - 1} + H \left(44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2} \right) \\ &= E_I H + H|A| \left(c - \frac{|I_H|}{N + H - 1} \right) + H \left(44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2} \right) \\ &\leq E_I H + H(44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2}), \end{aligned}$$

because $|I_H| \geq cN + H - 1$.

Finally we apply Cauchy inequality and Lemma 2.2 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} -E_I &\leq 44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2} + H^{-1} \sum_{n \in I_H} \left| A(n) - A(n - H) - \frac{H|A|}{N + H - 1} \right| \\ &\leq 44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2} + 2N^{-3/4}|I_H|^{1/2}D_H^{1/2} \\ &\leq 44N^{\frac{1}{4}} + 40N^{\frac{1}{8}}L_+^{\frac{1}{2}} + 2N^{\frac{-3}{4}} \left((cN)^{1/2} + (H + 1)^{1/2} \right) \left(\frac{\sqrt{3}HL_+^{1/2}}{N^{1/4}} + \frac{H^{3/2}}{N^{1/2}} + \sqrt{2}H^{1/2}N^{1/4} \right) \\ &\leq 44N^{1/4} + 40N^{1/8}L_+^{1/2} + 2N^{-3/4} \left(c^{1/2}N^{1/2} + \sqrt{2}N^{3/8} \right) \left(\sqrt{3}N^{1/2}L_+^{1/2} + N^{5/8} + \sqrt{2}N^{5/8} \right) \\ &\leq 52N^{1/4}(1 + c^{1/2}N^{1/8})(1 + L_+^{1/2}N^{-1/8}). \quad \square \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 2.3 and Lemma 2.4 imply Theorem 1.1. To prove Corollary 1.1, suppose that $A = N^{1/2} - L$, with $L_+ \leq kN^{1/4}$, and let I be any interval of length $k'N^{3/4}$. If we apply Lemma 2.4 we have

$$|A \cap I| > \frac{k'}{N^{1/4}}|A| - 52N^{1/4}(1 + k'^{1/2})(1 + k^{1/2}) > k'N^{1/4} - kk' - 52N^{1/4}(1 + k'^{1/2})(1 + k^{1/2}).$$

If we take k' large enough, $k' > 10000k$, then $|A \cap I| > 0$ for any interval of length greater than $k'N^{3/4}$.

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